

The Ability to Recall Dreams: A Thematic Overview

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KEYWORDS

*Dream recall,
EEG,
REM sleep,
cognition,
brain reactivity.*

ABSTRACT

Dreams are “a physiologically and psychologically conscious state that occurs during sleep and is often characterized by a rich array of endogenous sensory, motor, emotional, and other experiences” (APA). The ability of an individual to recall their dreams efficiently may be intertwined with their cognitive functions. This review paper seeks to study the different predictors on the ability to recall dreams. Research papers published between 2013 and 2023 were reviewed systematically and analyzed accordingly. Numerous findings were reported among which some researchers found intra-sleep awakenings are longer in high dream recallers than in low dream recallers. Significant differences in different sleep stages and brain reactivity were also described in some cases. Understanding the effects of various regions of the brain and effects of different cognitive factors may facilitate dream recall and enhance overall competency in various tasks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dreams are known to play crucial roles across various cultures [1]. Many of the tools that the early man used has been said to have come to their dreams [2]. Evidence can be found in the cave paintings and clay tablet journals of the Neanderthal period from 3000 B.C. According to dream researcher, Robert L. Van De Castle, “The cultural paths of these ancient civilizations were lit, not by electricity, but by the internal illumination provided by dreams”.

Various definitions of dreams have been given over the years to understand it better. According to Girindra Sekhar Bose, dreams are peculiar thought processes during the sleeping state [3]. While American Psychological Association (APA) defined it as, “a physiologically and psychologically conscious state that occurs during sleep and is often characterized by a rich array of endogenous sensory, motor, emotional, and other experiences.”

Dream of recall frequency or the ability of individuals to remember their dreams upon

awakening, is found to be affected by numerous factors, such as, creativity, openness to experience [4], attention [5], stress [6] among others.

According to Michael Foucault, the realm of imagination begins with dreams. Renaissance philosopher, Marsilio Ficino referred to it as “the vacancy of the soul”, when the soul is free from the physical being to achieve a greater, spiritual state. Over the decades, it is seen that many of the works of art are inspired by the dreams of the artist. The famous surrealist, Salvador Dali described his paintings as “hand-painted dream photographs.” Dreams are also known to contribute on literature often, two of the main scenes of Frankenstein were dreamed by Mary Shelley and R L Stevenson got some ideas for Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde from his dreams. Some of Rabindranath Tagore’s creations were also influenced by his dreams. Films and music are also widely known to be influenced by them. Filmmakers such as, Orson Welles, Akira Kurosawa, Ingmar Bergman have scenes or even entire films inspired by their dreams. Musicians ranging from Ludwig Van Beethoven, Guiseppe Tartini to Paul McCartney, Billy Joel, have all been inspired by their dreams in the making of at least one of their compositions. Srinivasa Ramanujan, the self-taught mathematical genius from India credited a great number of his complex mathematical solutions to the Goddess Mahalakshmi, who unfolded scrolls in his dreams.

Sexual contents are one of the most common themes in dreams [7]. According to Theresa Cheung, an author who has been researching dreams for 25 years, “Sex dreams allow your curiosity to cathartically express itself, but in a safe way that hurts nobody.”

The present study aims to compile most of the available research papers, articles, and texts to gain a better understanding of how dream recall is influenced by factors, such as, creativity, sexual desire, stress and vice versa. It also seeks to understand the various styles of dream interpretation.

2. METHOD

A comprehensive study was conducted encompassing research papers from Google scholar, PubMed and subscribed journals from University Library. Articles on the Indian and Western perspective of dreams were also included. Excerpts

from the research papers were divided based on the methodology of the respective studies and the findings. Studies were segmented based on their properties in high and low dream recallers and how dreams affect the mind of an average person.

I. Inclusion Criteria

Open-source research articles which are less than 15 years old (2008 to 2024) and those that worked with the general population were included.

II. Exclusion Criteria

Research articles older than 15 years are excluded unless they are classic literatures or important for the study conducted. Also, the research works working with a specific population are excluded.

III. Conceptual Review

The ancient Hindu texts on dreams can be found in the Vedas. There, dreams were seen in lieu of the objective world. Various factors including the time of the night, the temperament of the dreamer influences the type of dreams a person sees [8]. Temperament of a person according to the Vaisheshika Darshana (600-200 BC) is the Doshika dominance along the *prakriti* of a person. This is also the earliest account in the Hindu texts where the concepts of nightmares were elucidated.

The Mandukya Upanishad (700 BC) provides two theories on dreams: the first one states that they are a means of wish fulfilment. Interestingly, the same thoughts occurred to Freud which he later explained in the Interpretation of Dreams [9]. The second theory suggests, the soul of the dreamer leaves the body and gathers experiences right up to the point, they are awakened. Similar theories were presented in the west as well, though these are only speculations.

3. DISCUSSION

From the Mesopotamian era, clay tablets describing the sequential dreams of the legendary warrior, Gilgamesh has been discovered and it is found that his mother helped him in interpreting those dreams, making her the first dream therapist on record. For a long time, dreams were thought to be messages from the deep which were to guide people’s lives.

Though, previously, scientists did not give much significance to dreams and they used to believe it was some toxin or indigestion that made the brain to produce absurd imagery. But nevertheless, it has had

always had a great influence on the average human mind and from time immemorial, humans are seeking to interpret the meaning of their dreams.

Sigmund Freud first discovered a close relationship among mental disorders and dreams in his patients. His studies were the first scientific attempt that helped in unravelling the mysteries of dreams. In *The Interpretation of Dreams* (1899), he suggested that dreams are the royal road to the unconscious and are related to the events of the previous days.

Hall and Van de Castle (1966), while working on a new cognitive theory for dreaming, published a thorough content scoring system for dreams [10]. This stimulated works on dream researches and provided for a systematic method to study them.

See Appendix 1 containing the systemic review of the papers following PRISMA Guidelines (2020).

I. Dreams and Creativity

Barrett (2017) found that when posed with problems that have personal significance, it may increase dream creativity, thus, increasing out of the box thinking [11]. A recent study by Lacaux et. al. (2021) suggested that the steel ball technique used by Thomas Alva Edison actually works [12]. Salvador Dali used a similar technique but with the aid of a spoon. They used to nap with a steel ball or a spoon in their hands, and it would drop just as they were to fall asleep, thus helping them to capture creative ideas presented in their hypnagogic dreams. Celia Lacaux believes that spending a minimum of 15 seconds in the hypnagogic state may triple the chances of unleashing this hidden rule.

It has also been reported that people who are better in divergent style of creative thinking are better dream recallers than those better in convergent style, in a REM awakening design [13].

II. Dreams and Stress

According to Hartmann (1996), the dominant emotion as experienced by an individual, is contextualized in dreams, so, someone who experienced a traumatic event is more likely to have nightmares [14]. In a study conducted by Armitage (1992), it was found that a gender difference prevails in the ability to recall dreams from the effect of stress. Males reported a decrease in dream recall from low to

high stress days, whereas the recall rate of females increased on high stress days [15].

Evidences have also been found that dream recall increases in presence of naturally occurring stress, thus, providing some support to the general dream theories that to adapt to emotional difficulties during stress, an increase in dream rates may be seen [16].

III. Dreams and Sexual Desire

Freud suggested that dreams are an individual's repressed wishes in disguise, and as, sexual dreams often go against the existing social norms so, it is presented in form of various symbols. Contrary to Freud, Schredl et. al. (2019) reported the amount of time spent by an individual indulged in sexual thoughts and fantasies is related to the frequency of erotic dreams they experience [17].

IV. Dreams and Mental Imagery

Every person, when asleep, conducts an experiment through dreams. The dreamer, though disconnected from the environment, is highly conscious, and it is then that the brain creates various stories with actors and scenarios of its own.

Wilhelm Wundt believed that all thought processes are accompanied by images. Marks (1973) reported that people who recall more details in pictures are those who experience images vividly. Therefore, the dreamer may face some disorientation when differentiating between the dreaming and wakefulness consciousness [18]. Another study on dreams in children demonstrated that development through dream features resembles cognitive development in awake state [19].

Moreover, a person with a brain lesion, having significant impairment in waking cognition will also have parallel deficits in dreams. In an early case report by Charcot (1883), it was found that a patient with visual agnosia who was previously an excellent painter, linguist and classic scholar, was unable to form some mental images linked to his past memories [20]. It was also reported that the patient was deprived of visual experiences in dreams. The supramarginal gyrus that engages in the highest level of information processing of perception including symbolic operations, is also required for abstract thinking and in the retention of organized experience [21]. This very area is attributed by Solms (2000) as important for

dream formation, so a lesion in this region leads to the loss in dreaming [22].

As already stated in the lesion studies, an intact temporo-parieto-occipital junction is required for dreaming and is also related with wakefulness and mental imagery. Cognitive studies have shown that high visual-spatial skills are positively correlated with high rates of dream recall. A study by Hiscock & Cohen (1973) reported that high dream recallers have a greater capacity for visual imagery than low dream recallers. Even in children, it is observed that both dream recall and visual imagery develop simultaneously [23].

V. Dreams and Memory

As is already implied, there is an effect of memory on dreams. Various studies have attempted in studying that phenomenon over the years. There is converging evidences that suggests that the period during which a person dreams is when the memory networks are repetitively reactivated to stabilize and reorganize the obtained information in the long-term storage in the absence of any new external stimuli. This process contributes to conscious experience during sleep and facilitated dream recall [24].

Malinowski & Horton (2014), found that most dreams are the incorporation of autobiographical memories rather than episodic memories [25] also, Payne & Nadel (2004) suggested that during REM sleep, high levels of cortisol are observed which interferes with memory consolidation and affects the dream content [26].

Another study suggested that the frequency of black and white dreams that a person sees is negatively related to their colour memory and dream recall frequency. High-dream recallers are better at recalling the details of their dreams and observed their dreams to be black and white less often [27].

VI. Dreams and Substance Use

Substance use has some impact on the dream experience of an individual. Though the experience of dreams is affected by various factors, such as, interest in dreams and personality traits among other factors. The effect of drugs on sleep and on dreams tends to differ according to the stages of its usage, namely, intoxication, withdrawal and chronic use and cannabis withdrawal is found to induce strange dreams [28], and

similar dream patterns are also elicited during cocaine withdrawal [29]. But, mostly in a study by Nicolas & Ruby (2020), it was observed that antidepressants and sedatives reduce dream recall frequency as they enhance the dream quality of the person. While, psychotropic drugs were found to decrease intra-sleep awakenings [30].

VII. Dreams and Psychopathology

The existence of a psychopathology influences the dream content and the dream recall capacity of an individual. Conversely, the experience of a disturbing dream or a nightmare may trigger psychopathological distress. Nightmares are widely correlated with general levels of psychopathology and 'neuroticism' trait.

Environmental factors, such as, a traumatic event can have an effect on both dream content and pathological tendencies. Such an event makes the individual more vulnerable for the next traumatic experience and this stirs up an emotional turmoil in the individual's mind which then finds expression in their dreams. Psychopathology, in this aspect may be categorized into types, namely, those that are related to sleep and those that are not related to sleep, to study their impact on dream experiences. Therefore, those findings that involve sleep disorders are discussed here.

Influence of Sleep Disorders on Dreams

Insomnia is a disorder wherein the individual experiences deterioration of sleep. Though, the severity of insomnia plays an important role in this aspect but, both an increase [31] and a decrease in dream recall frequency is observed in patients with insomnia [32]. Schredl et. al. (2002) suggested that dream recall in insomniacs are higher due to their increased nighttime awakenings. The REM sleep instability hypothesis associated with this disorder results in a disruptive and non-restorative sleep [33].

Narcolepsy is a condition where the person experiences increased daytime drowsiness. This correlates with an increased dream recall frequency [34] as the cognitive processes involved in dream generation reach their optimal functioning faster for narcolepsy patients than for those who do not have this condition.

Studies on the association of dream recall with somnambulism and restless leg syndrome did not suggest much significant findings [35].

VIII. Physiology behind Dreams

The physiological mechanism behind dreaming is important to understand the high and low dream recall rates. Among the various stages of sleep, the REM sleep, i.e., the stage characterized by rapid eye movements, is when people usually dream and non-REM sleep is all the other stages of sleep except REM, where dreaming usually does not occur. Voss et. al. (2014) suggested a frontotemporal gamma electroencephalographic (EEG) activity is linked to the conscious awareness as experienced in dreams [36]. Asterisk and Kleitman (1953) who are attributed to be the first dream researchers to have a sleep research laboratory, found that 74.1 percent of participants reported to have recalled their dreams after waking from REM sleep while only 17.4 percent participants reported so after waking from non-REM sleep. Eichenlaub et. al. (2014) suggested that differences between these high and low dream recall rates are due to a particular cerebral functional organization. They also reported that and intra-sleep awakenings are greater in high recallers (HR) than in low recallers (LR) and both induce different brain responses to randomly presented sounds [37]. In 2017, in a study conducted by Vallat et. al., it was reported that the amount of intra-sleep awakening serves as an essential parameter for dream recall and it takes approximately 2 minutes for a successful encoding of dreams in the long-term memory. High recallers showed more arousing stimuli and more long awakenings than low recallers [38].

Nielsen et. al. (2015) administered two sleep-sensitive tasks on their participants – Corsi Block test, which is REM sleep sensitive and associated with number of REM awakenings for dream reporting and, Tower of Hanoi, which is NREM sleep sensitive and associated with sleep spindle density. They found significant association between the improvements of these tasks and changes in both REM and NREM sleep [39].

Siclari et. al. (2017) used a high-density electroencephalogram, to differentiate dreaming in REM and NREM sleep. It was found that dream experiences irrespective of REM or NREM sleep were

associated with local decreases in low-frequency activity in posterior cortical region but not with the recall of those experiences [40]. Various studies have been conducted on the difference in NREM sleep in high and low dream recallers.

Another important aspect is to understand that whether dreams are using a 'bottom-up' or 'top-down' approach, i.e., does the dreaming process begin at the low-level sensory perception which is then interpreted and accordingly synthesized by the higher order functioning, or does the process begin at the higher order abstract thinking, memories and wish-fulfilment region and is gradually enriched by the sensory perceptions. According to Freud and his followers, dreams have its roots in an individual's wishes, motives and needs that are later manifested by sensory percept. In 2022, Ruby et. al. conducted research to study the top-down and bottom-up attentional performance in high and low dream recallers using EEG and Competitive Attention Task. It was reported that increased bottom-up processes in high dream recallers would facilitate dream recall through awakening and increased top-down processes may foster it by increased awareness and short-term memory stability of dream content [41].

4. OVERALL FINDINGS

1. Dream content depends on different cognitive factors of the dreamer.
2. Dream content depends on personality of the dreamer.
3. Dream content depends on daily activities of the dreamer.
4. Dreams have been an intriguing aspect in both the Indian and Western societies and the concepts though stemming from dynamically different perspectives, are intertwined to some extent.
5. Dream content tends to inspire and enrich creativity.
6. Dream content depends on stress levels and may vary with gender.
7. Dream content depends on sexual desire of the dreamer.
8. Dream recalls and mental imagery tends to be intermingled since childhood.
9. Dream recall depends on the process of reorganizing information in long-term memory and

is mostly interrelated with autobiographical memory.

10. Dream recall depends on the type of substance used.

11. Dream recall depends on the presence or absence of a psychopathology.

5. CONCLUSION

The subject of dreams has been an intriguing domain since the dawn of time. Writers, researchers, painters or even average people, have all tried to find or associate some meaning to their dreams and also found some inspiration at times. The area of dreams is so vast and comprehensive that even after years of research, we still are far from comprehending it fully. But, from what we know, a person's personality characteristics, cognitive functions and their sense of well-being can all contribute to the differences in the contents of dreams and dream recall. An exploration of most of those factors is attempted through this review paper to provide guidance to future researchers.

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Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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Appendix I

Study	Sample	Materials	Analysis	Results
Cai et. al. (2009) [42]	N = 77 Age: 25-35	RAT, Polysomnography	ANOVA	Cholinergic and non-adrenergic neuromodulation during REM sleep facilitates problem solving.
Schredl (2009) [43]	N = 444 Mean Age: 23.5 +/- 5.7	Dream recall measures, personality measures, visual imagination measure, visual memory measure, sleep behaviour measure, stress measure	Correlation, regression analysis	Dream recall was found to be correlated with various factors in varying degrees, of which imagination and kindling interest in dreams was found to be leading factors in influencing dream recall
Funkhouser & Schredl (2010) [44]	N = 444 Mean Age: 23.5 +/- 5.7	Déjà rêve and dream recall frequency measure, attitude towards dream questionnaire, personality measures, creativity/fantasy measures	Regression analysis, correlation	Different personality types and dreaming experiences may prompt an individual into experiencing a higher frequency of déjà rêve (feeling that the current experience was already dreamed about by the individual)
Malinowski & Horton (2014) [25]	N = 32 Mean Age: 26.44	Dream and daily activities booklet, Pulse Smartpen and Dot paper	Descriptives, distribution percentages	Activity of autobiographical memory and processing was found to be more intertwined with dreams
Yu (2014) [45]	N = 564 Mean Age: 19.28	Dream Intensity Scale, Dream Motif Scale, Traumatic Experiences Checklist, Ko's Mental Health Questionnaire	Pearson χ^2 and Mann-Whitney U test	Dream content can help predict psychopathological tendencies
Bloxham (2018) [46]	N = 57 Mean Age: 23.7	MADRE	Correlation, ordinal regression	Dream recall tends to be greatly interlinked with the memory processes of an individual and with how fascinated they are in recalling and interpreting their dreams
Van Wyk et.	N = 36	Michigan Alcoholism	Inferential	Awakenings from

al. (2019) [47]		Screening Test, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index, Beck Depression Inventory (BDI-II), Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview, Shipley-2 IQ Test, EEG, EOG, EMG, ECG	statistics	non-REM sleep, especially from N2 are advantageous to high dream recall
Vallat et. al. (2022) [48]	N = 55 Mean Age: 22.55	MAGNETOM Prisma 3.0 T scanner, Big Five Inventory, State-Trait Anxiety Inventory, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index, MEM-III, Digit Span, Guildford's Alternative Uses Task	One-tailed <i>t</i> -test, two-sided <i>t</i> -test	Higher levels of creativity are associated with a higher dream recall rate.
Dijkstra & Fleming (2023) [49]	N = 272 and 339 for experiment 1 and 2 respectively Mean Age: 27.5	Vividness of Visual Imagery Questionnaire, Standard Forced-Choice Discrimination Task	Binary Logistic Regression, Multinomial Ordinal Regression	Both imagery and perception tend to be intermingled. So, reality judgment is based on their respective signal strength and imagery vividness.

